
Influence of sunshine on GDP per capita

A Data Management Plan created using dmponline

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Template: DCC Template

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Project abstract:

This paper explores the hypothesis that dreary weather discourages people from going outside and in turn makes them more productive. Likewise, that beautiful weather outside distracts people from their work, which should reflect in a country's GDP per capita. We use some basic statistical indicators to show that further exploration of this topic is a valid research path, but better-quality weather data is needed to make conclusions.

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Data Collection

What data will you collect or create?

This paper uses 3 existing, external datasets:

1. **GDP per capita** from <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.PCAP.CD> (accessed on 13.04.2021)
 - o File location: `input_data/API_NY.GDP.PCAP.CD_DS2_en_csv_v2_2163510/API_NY.GDP.PCAP.CD_DS2_en_csv_v2_2163510.csv`
 - o File size: 258.5KiB
 - o Format: csv
 - o Description: This dataset contains GDP per capita data on most countries in the world starting from the 1960s, all the way up to 2019, at the time of accessing the dataset.
 - o Justification: The World Bank is regarded as a reliable source of data by countless scientific publications, which is why we decided to use it. The csv file format was used for simplicity and interoperability, but XML and XLS are also available, with the latter one potentially considered as proprietary. The size of volume of data in this case allows for flexible storage, and safekeeping together with the source code in a code repository like Github.
2. **World cities ranked by annual sunshine hours** from <https://data.world/makeovermonday/2019w44>, which is a snapshot from 2019 of https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_cities_by_sunshine_duration.
 - o File location: `input_data/Cities by Sunshine Duration.xlsx`
 - o File size: 43.3KiB
 - o Format: xlsx
 - o Description: This is a community-maintained dataset on average hours of sunshine in different cities across the world. The meaning of "sunshine" in this case are the actual sun rays that reach the ground, unblocked by clouds. This makes it a good indicator of how cloudy a place is, and how sunny it is perceived to be.
 - o Justification: We rightfully admit that both the source, and the format of this dataset leave much to be desired. However, it was surprisingly hard to find such data on a global scale. Considering how the wikipedia page, on which this dataset is hosted on, has over 190 references, it is unlikely that a group of people would go through so much trouble to curate this data if it was readily accessible somewhere else. The xlsx file from data.world was used since the original dataset was only present as an HTML table, which would have to be scraped. We consider an xlsx file to be more accessible than such a format, even though it is proprietary.
3. **Geometric data on country borders** from <https://www.naturalearthdata.com/downloads/10m-cultural-vectors/10m-admin-0-countries/>
 - o File(s) location: `input_data/file:///shared/Documents/Fakultet/SS2021/Data_Stewardship/Ex1/Project/input_data/ne_10m_admin_0_countries/`
 - o Total size: 9.0 MiB
 - o Formats: shp, shx, dbf, prj, cpg
 - o Description: This dataset contains community-made high-resolution geospatial data on 247 countries in the world. It is used for producing the final world map visualizations in our paper.
 - o Justification: This dataset is a well known and well used source of geospatial data. The formats which make it up are considered mostly open in the field of cartography, though some specialist, albeit open-source software is needed to open it. Geopandas, a well-known library for python3, can open these files without any issues.

We create four artifacts:

1. **The code itself**, as a Jupyter notebook called `gdp-sunshine.ipynb`. While the file size is fairly big relative to files usually stored in a code repository like GitHub (at just under 30MiB), we still decided not to remove the output cells which make up most of the data, because GitHub provides a useful preview feature for jupyter notebooks. The jupyter file format is an open standard and is widely used in the data science community. The content itself is written in python3, using some well known and widely used libraries like Pandas, Numpy and Matplotlib. The versions are saved in the `Pipfile.lock` (managed by pipenv), to ensure the best possible reproducibility of the test environment.
2. **The merged dataset**, as a csv file called `gdp_sunshine.csv`. This is the output of our processing pipeline and the basis for the visualization. The size is about 12KiB.
3. **The world map visualization**, as a PDF `sunshine_gdp_world.pdf`. This contains two world maps, colored by the respective intensity of yearly sunny hours in a country and the country's GDP per capita, if available. We decided to export a pdf instead of a rasterized image because the vector data allows for arbitrary resizing.
4. **The Pearson correlation matrix**, as a PDF `sunshine_gdp_corr.pdf`. The file size is about 14KiB. The decision was made to export the correlation matrix visually, as simple row-based data formats like csv are not really meant for such outputs (at least without extra documentation). This data can easily be reconstructed from the merged dataset if needed.

How will the data be collected or created?

All input datasets, found in the "input_data" folder, are pre-existing datasets that can be found openly online. We keep the original file/folder names.

In terms of output, we produce three files in the "output" folder, and the code in the root directory. All three artifacts are

explained in the previous question.

For file versioning we used git. After the initial download date (also noted above), we haven't updated any of our input data.

Documentation and Metadata

What documentation and metadata will accompany the data?

The entry point to the documentation is the README.md file located in the root directory. It contains basic information such as the DOIs of data found in the project, the directory structure with comments on the most important artifacts, a data-flow diagram and instructions on how to reproduce the experiment environment.

Since the entire source code is in python3, more precisely a Jupyter notebook, dependency management is achieved using the **pipenv** tool. This tool creates the files **Pipfile** and **Pipfile.lock**, which ensure a reproducible execution environment, going beyond the traditional requirements.txt file. This way of dependency management in python is considered to be the new de-facto standard as it solves many potential issues that arise from mismatched package versions.

The **documentation** folder contains the data flow diagram in the svg format, with extra embedded data for draw.io, an open-source diagram drawing tool used to create it. Furthermore all of the metadata manually created in this project is contained in this folder:

- **metadata.xml** - Contains the Dublin Core metadata on the code (notebook). It also serves as the metadata file for the whole project.
- **sunshine_gdp_corr-metadata.xml** and **sunshine_gdp_world-metadata.xml** - Also contain machine-actionable Dublin Core metadata on the two respective output artifacts. Since these were vector images, we decided that the Dublin Core vocabulary is expressive enough. Any file-specific extensions are contained in the files themselves and would be realistically needed only when opening the files.
- **gdp_sunshine-metadata.json** - This is a machine-actionable metadata file based on [W3C's csv on the web](#) recommendation, using again the Dublin Core vocabulary as the base. We decided to adopt this standard, as it was pretty much the only well thought-out option for annotating CSVs. Aside from the usual Dublin Core information, the metadata contains a description and type information on all columns in the csv. It must be noted however, that this recommendation still hasn't received wide adoption and that our hand-written implementation might not be 100% up to the original spec. This is due to the current lack of tools supporting this standard.

For describing the media types in every metadata file, we used the [IANA Media Type vocabulary](#).

Finally, since all of the produced artifacts will be uploaded to Zenodo, their own version of metadata will be available for download in different machine-actionable formats. This format contains further information on the exact relation type between all of the referenced data.

Ethics and Legal Compliance

How will you manage any ethical issues?

There are no ethical considerations needed for the data used or produced, on one hand due to the data itself, and on the other, due to the open nature of its publishing. That is to say, we haven't produced or used anything that wasn't otherwise freely available and accessible by everyone. We have also followed the TU Wien's data protection policy in this matter.

The only part which could be considered politically sensitive is the world map produced, as there are definitely some disputed territories shown in the image. We consider this issue unavoidable without considerable effort needed to adapt the artifact to every single political view out there.

How will you manage copyright and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues?

Since the weather data is covered by the CC BY-SA license, and that is the most restrictive one out of all the input datasets, we are obliged to also use this license for all of the artifacts produced, including the Jupyter notebook, as they could all be legally considered derivatives and remixes of this dataset. Other than that, we have the right to make copies of the data and host it on private and public repositories with open access.

The copyright owner is [Filip Darmanovic](#)

Storage and Backup

How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?

Since the size of the entire project is relatively small, it can be stored in its entirety in a code repository (in our case we chose GitHub). Additionally, a corresponding repository on zenodo will be created which mirrors every release from GitHub. Generally, these two are one of the world's largest repositories for their respective use and are considered more than reliable enough for our use case. In case of data loss, any person with internet access can easily download the latest data from any of those two services.

Additionally, to prevent data loss between commits, all research is conducted on a personal computer running ZFS storage in a mirrored configuration, similar to RAID1. This protects not only against total hardware failure, but also bit rot, potentially caused by electromagnetic radiation or minor hardware issues.

The responsible person for committing data to the repository regularly is Filip Darmanovic

How will you manage access and security?

Since the data used and produced in this project is completely openly accessible, most of the security and privacy concerns don't apply. The only possible issue would be someone changing the public repository and potentially injecting some malicious code, but that's mitigated by only one person (Filip Darmanovic) having write access to the uploaded data through a 2FA-secured account.

One thing we cannot ensure however is that the produced data and its derivatives will be re-published in the same CC BY-SA license.

Selection and Preservation

Which data are of long-term value and should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?

While most important artifacts of this research are the Jupyter notebook, the pipeline output as csv, and the Pipfile.lock file, the size of the entire project is small enough for the repositories we used to preserve the entire thing long after the research might be considered relevant. There are no legal or similar requirements that prohibit such preservation of data.

The foreseeable research uses are different interpretations of the generated output, or simply references to past research.

What is the long-term preservation plan for the dataset?

Zenodo, according to their [policy](#), promises to keep all data accessible for at least 20 years, and [GitHub's archive program](#) aims to preserve all enabled repositories for about 1000 years. This is all provided free of charge for such relatively small datasets.

Data Sharing

How will you share the data?

As previously mentioned, all of the data will be publicly accessible either through GitHub or Zenodo. We decided to create a separate DOI for the code and each of the 3 artifacts in the output folder. All of these artifacts will be separately hosted on zenodo together with their metadata, in addition to the entire project's landing page. We tried to cross-reference the artifacts to the best of our abilities to ensure better discoverability.

Searchability is supported by the keywords which accompany each artifact (indexed both in GitHub and Zenodo).

Are any restrictions on data sharing required?

There are no restrictions on data sharing, apart from acting according to the license.

Responsibilities and Resources

Who will be responsible for data management?

Every role in this project is fulfilled by [Filip Darmanovic](#). However, ensuring that the chosen repositories uphold their own policies is not in his jurisdiction.

What resources will you require to deliver your plan?

Apart from time, there are no additional resources required for executing the plan outlined in this DMP, as the amount of data is fairly small.